

Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science services - CORBEL -

Deliverable D9.1

Refined organisational competency framework needed by distributed RIs
at 3 development stages

WP9 – Training

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Executive Summary

The goal of this deliverable is to define the competencies required by technical operators of RIs by seeking input from experts in the four target areas defined by the CORBEL project as a whole – data management and integration, physical access, ethics and innovation – from within and beyond the BMS-RIs. We have capitalised on the experience that we have gained together in the EMTRAIN consortium, using methodologies that we are currently refining (www.lifetrain.eu), to document, gain broad buy-in for, and maintain competency profiles for technical roles.

Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached the following objectives:

- a) Define competency requirements for technical operators of BMS RIs.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background

CORBEL will create a platform for harmonised user access to biological and medical technologies, biological samples and data services required by cutting-edge biomedical research, thereby boosting the efficiency, productivity and impact of European biomedical research. To achieve this, the technical operators of the 11 research infrastructures that form the CORBEL consortium need to develop a shared understanding of the knowledge, skills and behaviours required to deliver on CORBEL's four major themes:

- Harmonised user access to research infrastructures
- Unified data management
- Common ethical and legal services
- Joint innovation support

Technical operation of biomedical research infrastructures covers a wide range of different roles and types of service. We consider individuals contributing to the technical provision of the following to be within scope:

- Data services (e.g. databases, software tools, controlled vocabularies)
- Biosample services (e.g. collections of mice, microorganisms, cell lines, seeds, patient samples)
- Facilities requiring physical access (e.g. facilities for imaging, structural biology, use of pathogenic micro-organisms, marine stations, some high-end computing facilities).

We do not consider RI professionals in non-technical roles, such as HR, communications, project management or finance to be within scope; their roles are covered by a complementary project, RItrain (<http://ritrain.eu/>).

- We are using a competency-based approach to developing, delivering and monitoring the CORBEL training programme. As summarised above, CORBEL (<http://www.corbel-project.eu/>) is developing training for technical operators of biomedical research infrastructure. We are adopting the same approach in several other projects in which research infrastructures are working together to develop training for operators, managers and users of research infrastructures:
- RItrain (<http://ritrain.eu/>) is developing training for managers and leaders of research infrastructure
- BioExcel (<http://bioexcel.eu/>) is developing training for users of research infrastructure (specifically users of biomodelling and simulation tools, including in an HTC and HPC context)
- ELIXIR-EXCELERATE (<https://www.elixir-europe.org/excelerate>) is developing training for researchers, developers of bioinformatics infrastructure and trainers

We are using similar tools and methodologies to define competency in each of these projects, with the goal of ensuring that the competency profiles, and the resulting training programmes developed from them, are complementary.

Competency is an observable ability of any professional, integrating multiple components such as knowledge, skills, values and attitudes. It is observable, so its acquisition can be validated objectively. Competency provides a shared ‘currency’ applicable to learning of all types and at all career stages:

- Individual professionals can use competency as a career development tool: by documenting the competencies that you have gained, and the evidence that you have gained them, in a competency portfolio you can seek further training to fill gaps in your portfolio, or map your existing portfolio to roles that you might not previously have considered.
- Professional bodies and employers can use competency to define competency profiles for different roles or professions. These provide useful guidance when hiring and promoting individuals, and can also provide the basis for professional recognition in regulated professions.
- Course providers can use competency to develop training (by asking what competencies their trainees need to gain) and, where appropriate, to assess whether training has been effective.

A **competency profile** defines the competencies required to fulfil a particular role. In the biomedical sciences, a number of professional bodies and learned societies have begun to take this approach. The research infrastructures involved in CORBEL have also worked together, and in collaboration with several multinational pharmaceutical companies as part of the IMI’s EMTRAIN (<http://www.emtrain.eu/>) project. LifeTrain (<http://www.lifetrain.eu/>) – a competency-based framework for education and training in the biomedical sciences – has been a major deliverable of the EMTRAIN project in collaboration with the other IMI Education and Training projects (IMItrain <http://www.imi-train.eu/>). IMItrain has tested the competency-based approach and developed

competency profiles for medicines development and safety sciences. LifeTrain is collecting competency profiles (<http://www.lifetrain.eu/competencies/competency-profiles/>) to make it easier for the biomedical research community to identify and use them. This body of work inspired us, and brought together the right people, to develop competency-based training for the biomedical research infrastructures.

Our work plan for CORBEL WP9 is summarised in figure 1. This deliverable provides the foundation for this work:

Figure 1: The work plan for CORBEL WP9.

Description of Work

Task 9.1 Definition of competency requirements. Partners: BBMRI-ERIC, EATRIS, ECRIN-ERIC, INFRAFRONTIER, EMBL-ELIXIR, Imperial (ISBE), IMG (Euro-Biolmaging), UU (EU-OPENSREEN), UMinho (MIRRI) and STFC (INSTRUCT).

We have defined the competencies required by technical operators of RIs by seeking input from experts in the four target areas defined above – from within and beyond the BMS-RIs. We capitalised on the experience that we have gained together in the EMTRAIN consortium, using methodologies developed as part of the IMI-funded IMItrain project, to document, gain broad buy-in for, and maintain competency profiles for technical roles.

Survey of training needs

We began this task by surveying both technical operators and managers/leaders of research infrastructures to find out more about their perceived training needs. Rather than risking bombarding the same audience with multiple, closely related, surveys, we incorporated our questions into a survey for RItrain WP2. The survey is available at <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/FDQZBV5> and a PDF version is provided in Appendix 1, with the questions of particular relevance to CORBEL WP9 highlighted in yellow.

The survey was distributed by email on 19 Jan 2016 to >170 hand-selected individuals representing managerial, technical and training representatives of the ESFRI and EIROForum research infrastructures. Heads of the hubs of distributed research infrastructures were encouraged to distribute the survey to their nodes, to ensure that we gathered information on the training needs of both the hubs and the nodes. The survey remains open, although our contacts were asked to complete the survey by 9 February so that we would have significant input on RI training needs to inform two interactive back-to-back workshops in which we defined the competency requirements for both RItrain and CORBEL. Again, these two workshops were designed to complement each other; only the second workshop forms part of this deliverable.

A full analysis of the survey results will be reported in RItrain D3.3. Regarding the responses pertaining to technical operation of research infrastructures, the highest priority training needs were (1) Infrastructure and research management (28.17% of respondents) and (2) Service provision (18.31% of respondents).

Regarding the question ‘Please summarise what your infrastructure would be able to do (or be able to do better) as a consequence of the training’, figure 2 provides a word cloud of the responses.

Figure 2: word cloud of responses to the question ‘Please summarise what your infrastructure would be able to do (or be able to do better) as a consequence of the training’.

Workshop to define training needs for technical operators of research infrastructures

The workshop – entitled Addressing skills gaps in technical operation of biomedical research infrastructures – took place on 17 and 18 February 2016; the programme is available at <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/events/2016/addressing-skills-gaps-technical-operation-biomedical-research-infrastructures>. We had 13 participants plus 8 speakers (21 in total) representing 8 research infrastructures: ECRIN, ELIXIR, the UK data archive (a node of CESSDA), EuroBioImaging, EGI, BBMRI, INFRAFRONTIER and EATRIS. Furthermore, we invited Yuri Demchenko, the coordinator of the EDISON project (<http://edison-project.eu/>), which is developing a competency-based curriculum for data science. This was extremely helpful as Edison has been tailoring eCF-3 (<http://www.ecompetences.eu/>), the European competency profile for ICT, to its needs. We used this as the basis for our discussions around both user access and data management.

During the workshop, use cases were presented on ELSI (Michaela Mayrhofer, BBMRI), Innovation (Anton Ussi, EATRIS), training the trainer (Stefan Terjung, EuroBioImaging) and user access (Sabine Fessele, INFRAFRONTIER). Each of these use-case presentations summarised skills needs in the relevant area, and provided a firm basis for two breakout sessions. In the first breakout, we tackled a very rough draft of a competency profile for technical operators of research infrastructures. This had been constructed before the workshop by reviewing the training needs identified in the survey and selecting relevant competencies from other, related profiles (eCF-3; Vitae's Researcher Development Framework; the ISCB's competency profile for bioinformaticians, and some of the generic competencies identified by IMITrain). In the first breakout, we divided into three groups: to consider the competencies required for (1) provision of access to research infrastructures/core facilities; (2) data science, and (3) ethics and innovation. The focus was entirely on the competencies required by technical operators of RIs and we encouraged the breakout groups to concentrate on areas of common ground among the different types of RI represented; we did not discuss competencies required by users of RIs although we did consider user training by technical operators to be within scope. Each group selected its top five priorities in terms of competency requirements and presented these back to the main group.

The outcomes of this exercise were consolidated, and in the second breakout group, we divided into the same groups again and defined the knowledge, skills and behaviours associated with each of the priority competency areas. This information was used to compile our refined competency profile, which forms the main deliverable of this report and is openly accessible here:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1j7cmC8hDWbAe8AiNNUYcv3fqjil-KA-trfBf6Wvi3UI/edit?usp=sharing>.

Another important outcome of the workshop is that several of the breakout groups identified training courses that already exist, and that might either be adapted to fulfil CORBEL's training needs or might already be suitable as they stand. A list of these has been made available in on-course® (https://www.on-course.eu/?q=&professional_bodies=29) – EMTRAIN's catalogue of learning

opportunities in the biomedical sciences. It is possible to filter for these courses by checking the 'Relevant to CORBEL' checkbox in the on course® advanced search box.

The screenshot shows the 'on-course' website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Courses', 'Provider', 'Quality Standards', 'About on-course', and 'PhD'. A search bar is prominently displayed with the text 'Search for courses now' and a 'Search' button. Below the search bar, there are filters for 'Short courses (CPD)', 'Masters', and 'PhD'. The 'Advanced Search' section is active, with 'Relevant to CORBEL' selected. A dropdown menu for 'Recognised by' is open, showing a list of accreditation bodies, with 'Relevant to CORBEL' checked. Two course listings are visible: 'FitSM Foundation Training' and 'FitSM Advanced Training in Service Operation and Control'. Both courses are offered by 'European Grid Infrastructure (EFI)' and are located in 'Amsterdam, Netherlands'. The first course is a 'Short courses' type, 8 hours long. The second course is a 'Short courses (CPD)' type, 15 hours long, with a start date of '10 May 2016' and a total cost of 'EUR 780.00'. A 'Detailed Description' button is present for each course listing.

Figure 2: Selecting courses that are especially relevant to technical operators of research infrastructures in on-course®.

Final outcome of the workshop: the CORBEL competency profile

The final outcome of the workshop is a refined competency framework that defines the highest priority training needs of CORBEL's technical operators at each phase of the RI life cycle – planning (P), construction (C) and operation (O). We have focused on areas that are of common interest to all the biomedical RIs and that will support them to deliver on the CORBEL project. The purpose of the profile is to enable us to find existing training that's fit for purpose and develop new courses; in its current form it is not intended for use by course seekers.

We would like to offer special thanks to Veronique Percheron of the European Space Agency for sharing the ESA Competency Framework (http://esamultimedia.esa.int/docs/careers/ESA_Competency_Framework.pdf). Many of the

behavioural competencies listed below are derived directly from this. We would also like to offer special thanks to Yuri Demchenko, the coordinator of the EDISON (<http://edison-project.eu/>) project. EDISON's amendments to the European e-Competence framework, e-CF-3.0 (<http://www.ecompetences.eu/e-cf-3-0-download/>), were invaluable in shaping the section on Technical Operation of Services and we plan to continue to align with EDISON as both projects evolve.

A 'living' version of this document, which is open to consultation from the broader community, is available at

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1j7cmC8hDWbAe8AiNNUYCv3fqjil-KA-trfBf6Wvi3UI/edit?usp=sharing>.

As with any new framework (competency-based or otherwise), there are areas for improvement and we anticipate that the current framework will be revised, both in light of changing needs and in light of feedback from training.

The coding of the profile into different sections (A-H) is based on eCF-3, enabling us to map back to this and track evolution of Edison's competency framework; to ensure that we focused on high priority areas for the CORBEL project, we were selective so not all the competencies in eCF-3 have an equivalent in our framework; furthermore we have added new sections (F-H) on generic and ELSI-related competencies.

Domain	Competence	Group	Phase*
Technical operation of services (A service may fall into any of the following categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data services (e.g. databases, software tools, controlled vocabularies) • Biosample services (e.g. collections of mice, microorganisms, cell lines, seeds, patient samples) • Facilities requiring physical access (e.g. facilities for imaging, structural biology, use of pathogenic micro-organisms, marine stations, some high-end computing facilities) 			
A. Planning and designing		Core	
A.7. Technology trend monitoring and innovation	Knowledge base <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the field appropriate to the role • Knowing who to ask, and where to get information on new developments • Monitors competitor activity in related areas Skills base <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributes to the broader community of technical operators within and beyond the organisation • Communicates discovery of potentially relevant technical solutions to others • Balances time between technology trend 	Core, Data	P, C, O

	<p>monitoring and working on current projects</p> <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Demonstrates interest in and enthusiasm for his/her field ● Demonstrates curiosity for developments outside the immediate field and how they might apply to own service ('thinking outside the box') ● Fosters an open-minded atmosphere among team members and broader community of collaborators ● Starts with what's required by users of the service and puts new trends into this context <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Is narrow minded - only considering innovations that are obviously connected to own field ● Is unable to recognise the need for improvement 		
A.8. Sustainable development and maintenance of existing services	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Knows where to apply for funding ● Understands internal organisational processes ● Knowledge of the field appropriate to the role <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Uses appropriate methods to raise awareness of services to the user community (marketing, outreach and communications skills) ● Uses project management, conflict management and negotiation skills effectively to ensure that services remain stable and that they continually improve in accord with user needs ● Monitors risks and takes appropriate steps to mitigate them ● Applies principles of business management to services, to ensure that they remain viable <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Anticipates the need for sustainability at the beginning of a project ● Persistent and assertive ● Convinces others of the need to maintain or develop the service ● Demonstrates resilience and doesn't take 		

	<p>setbacks personally</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sees the bigger picture - such as how own service fits into the organisational and wider landscape <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Behaves aggressively or impolitely - defending own service at all costs, regardless of the evidence 		
C. Operating and maintaining			
C.1. User Support	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Broad appreciation (ideally from personal experience) of users' activities and workflows, and of how own service fits into this broader context Awareness of customer support practices Knowledge of the organisation's portfolio of services and how own service fits into it Knowledge of organisational processes and policies <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication and interpersonal skills User training/facilitation skills Observational skills User experience skills, including user requirements/needs collection Problem identification and solving <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Empathises with users and strives to increase their satisfaction with the service Open mindset to new opportunities and change - agile/responsive Understands the sensitivity of customer-supplier relationships and acts accordingly Solves customer problems quickly and effectively Is able to identify existing and new customers and considers how to meet their needs Manages customer expectations in a manner that always provides satisfaction Seeks out and acts on customer feedback to improve the customer experience and increase satisfaction Demonstrates understanding of customers' 	<p>Courses - Train the trainer (adapt for ESFRI-BMS); Project management; communications / interpersonal skills; Problem solving + conflict management (U. HD but may not include scientific problem solving); cross-cultural training.</p>	C, O

	<p>immediate, as well as long-term goals and strategies and works accordingly</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anticipates customer problems <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not empathise with users; automatically thinks their inability to use a service is the user's fault and not an issue with the service • Does not know how to deal with unreasonable demands - fails to manage user expectations • Unfriendly/unwelcoming towards users • Does not know, realise or acknowledge that there is a user • Does not respond or responds slowly to user needs • Has no idea of what is expected by the user; makes assumptions about user needs • Does not look for feedback from users • Is unwilling to accept change 		
C.4. Problem solving (including people and scientific problem solving - aligned with RItrain)	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understands relevant methodologies and techniques for identifying, analysing and solving problems • Is aware of previous similar problems and draws on experience <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses a variety of analytical techniques and tools appropriate to the context to analyse and solve the problem • Able to recognise the urgency and importance of known and unprecedented problems and knows what to focus on as a priority for resolution • Follows a structured, systematic approach to analyse and solve known problems • Able to organise and seek the appropriate help to solve the problem in the organisational context <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Willing to identify and describe the problem • Follows problems through to their resolution • Seeks out all relevant facts associated with the problem, captures information rapidly, identifies pertinent issues and acts accordingly • Collects, processes and evaluates information in a systematic way • Learns from resolution of problems and puts general measures in place to prevent 	Core	(P), C, O

	<p>reoccurrence of problems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Able to adopt a damage control approach; is confident in unexpected situations and takes decisive action to prevent or minimise the negative effects of a problem <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not recognize problems, has a narrow-minded scope or allows problems to fester • Not able to judge quality of data • Acts on incomplete data • Uses no or inappropriate methods to analyse and solve the problem 		
C.6a. Service delivery	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data protection • Mission and service definition • Service delivery models (+ specific to data services) • Data and metadata identification and structure • Standards and best practices (including data formats; data handling) • Open data principles and access <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisational skills • Data management and planning (with respect to EC policy and those of local funders) • Implementation • Relevant data tools • Data annotation • Data curation • Communication • Managing expectations <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service/User-oriented mindset • Attention to detail • Solves customer problems quickly and effectively • Follows service delivery best practice • Complies with documented best practices • Strives for continuous improvement • Mindset for sustainability <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sloppy attention to detail • Pursues personal research agendas • Does not know or realise there is a customer • Does not respond or responds slowly to 	Data: courses - EUDAT (inc. webinars); RDA; ELIXIR; EGI-FITSM	C, O

	<p>customer needs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has no idea of what is expected by the customer; makes assumptions about customer needs • Does not know how to react to unreasonable customer demands • Does not look for feedback from customer • Is unwilling to accept change 		
C6b. Quality data monitoring	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assesses the quality, integrity and authenticity of data • Defines, collects and monitors appropriate data to answer specific questions relevant to the strategy of the organisation • Systematically collects user feedback and incorporates this into the improvement of quality • Links data appropriately • Appreciates the principles of data protection and applies them appropriately <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical skills • Data presentation skills • Applies quality assessment and data curation principles to create robust processes for the improvement and monitoring of data quality <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitors and evaluates progress, impact and outcomes of the team's/department's/organisation's deliverables • Applies a methodical and systematic approach to data acquisition, quality monitoring, enabling assessment of trends in service delivery over appropriate timescales • Pays attention to detail, looking for outliers in the data and seeking rational explanations for them • Demonstrates Integrity and objectivity when monitoring data quality, and seeks independent advice/opinion when appropriate <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not appreciate the value of quality monitoring to the organisation 	<p>Look at the Digital Curation Centre (Edinburgh; Joy Davidson)</p>	O

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does not seek to change behaviours or processes in the face of evidence that change would improve the service offered 		
D. Enabling			
D.11. Identification and understanding of user needs	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Appreciates the importance of user experience Understands how to create and analyse user surveys Customer relationship management (CRM) practices <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> User requirements/needs collection Ability to differentiate wants from needs Expectations management <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open mindset to new opportunities and change Understands the sensitivity of customer-supplier relationships and acts accordingly Solves customer problems quickly and effectively Is able to identify existing and new customers and considers how to meet their needs Manages customer expectations in a manner that always provides satisfaction Seeks out and acts on customer feedback to improve the customer experience and increase satisfaction Demonstrates understanding of customers' immediate, as well as long-term goals and strategies and works accordingly Anticipates customer problems <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does not know or realise there is a customer Does not respond or responds slowly to customer needs Has no idea of what is expected by the customer; makes assumptions about customer needs Does not know how to react to unreasonable customer demands Does not look for feedback from customer 	Data, ELI	P, C, O

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is unwilling to accept change 		
D.13. Data presentation/ visualisation, actionable data extraction	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accesses, integrates and critically analyses data from multiple sources Selects appropriate data analysis and visualisation methods for the data Translates complex concepts into clear outputs appropriate for the user group <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate statistical and data analysis skills appropriate to the role Demonstrate data visualisation skills appropriate to the role/ visualises complex and variable data <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consults with appropriate experts to ensure that appropriate data sets, analytical methods and visualisation methods are used Engages in continuing professional development to remain up-date on the latest data resources and methods Focuses on the needs and desires of the service user Continuously optimises processes Improves processes and services according to the needs of service users <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is not able to critically analyse and interpret service data and information from different sources Is not able to translate complex information into formats that facilitate users' workflows Is not able to implement successful collaborative working with others 	Data: courses - UK data service (info from David Hall; Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) ; focus on metadata; King's College/Berlin	C, O
D.15. Data management/pre-preservation/curation with data and insight (aligned with EDISON D2.1_CFDS)	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knows where to find, and how to effectively mine, relevant data including unstructured sources such as the scientific literature and structured sources such as public data Awareness/working knowledge of data models and different types of database Knows where to find and use relevant data standards <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develops and/or implements organisational data strategy Develops and or makes use of data models 	Data	C, O

	<p>including metadata</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrates different data sources and provides for further analysis by others Develops and maintains a historical data repository with appropriate version control Collects and manages different sources of data <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is methodical and consistent in approach to data management/curation Contributes to the broader community of data providers and curators Contributes to the development and optimal use of data standards Aims for a balance between usability and rigor Pursues opportunities to engage with users and understand their needs and frustrations <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pursues perfection to the detriment of completion or usability Lacks a methodical or consistent approach to data management Does not track major changes to data and who made them Does not contribute to relevant community initiatives Is un-empathic towards the needs of the user 		
Generic competences			
<p>Upholding organisational values: F.3. Cross-cultural and cross-disciplinary sensitivity (need to align with Rltrain)</p>	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Background knowledge of European history and how this has shaped policy Awareness of/familiarity with cultural differences and how they shape the behaviour of individuals Awareness of/familiarity with other disciplines and their relationship to own discipline <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> communication skills Basic command of non-native languages - even if only enough to say hello or order a beer! Patience/tolerance Sense of humour <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is conscious that other people, organisations and disciplines do things differently 		P, C, O

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Actively improves own knowledge and understanding of other countries and cultures ● Actively improves own knowledge and understanding of other disciplines ● Is aware of cultural differences in social and professional norms and effectively modifies or adapts own style and professional practices accordingly ● Confronts culturally or nationally discriminatory modes of behaviour ● Actively creates an atmosphere of cross-cultural learning and acceptance ● Creates a work environment in which cultural differences are understood and valued as a strength for the organisation ● Actively promotes cultural and national diversity in the organisation (e.g. in working groups, teams and selection processes) <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lacks knowledge and understanding of other European countries and cultures, and shows no curiosity to learn about them ● Tends to favour those who have the same cultural / national / disciplinary background; comes across as intolerant of difference (e.g. biologists' hatred of medics!) ● Frequently gives stereotypical interpretations of the behaviour of colleagues of different nationalities ● Believes there's only one best national way to do things ● Ignores cultural differences between different audiences and does not tailor approach accordingly 		
<p>Working together: H.1. Communication and interpersonal skills (need to align with Rltrain - interpersonal skills could be aligned with 'acting as a role model')</p>	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Broad understanding of communication models ● Can distinguish between different target audiences and identify the most appropriate means of reaching them ● Understands the science/technology underlying the research infrastructure and the services that it provides to be able to communicate effectively about them to different audiences <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fluent in the language in which the majority of communications are made ● Basic command of other languages ● Active listening skills ● Sympathetic ● Enthusiastic ● Appreciates the value of social media and uses it effectively to communicate effectively with 	Core	P, C, O

	<p>different audiences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Able to work effectively with creative professionals (e.g. designers, animators, journalists) • Interviewing skills <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicates clearly and precisely with people at all levels • Delivers points in a structured and logical manner • Informs others of relevant information appropriately and on time • Seeks out openness from others; gives straightforward, candid opinions to all • Invites two-way communication; actively listens/pays attention; able to engender participation and commitment from others • Communicates effectively even in difficult situations • Anticipates audience needs and tailors communications to the audience and the context • Proactive in discovering different audiences and their interests <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is unable to communicate the appropriate message • Does not inform others; forgets that communication is part of work • Does not participate in two-way communication when invited • Communicates in an indirect or vague way; tells others what they want to hear • Does not take into account, understand or accept perspective or needs of audience • Ignores cultural differences between different audiences and does not tailor approach accordingly 		
Ethics, law and innovation-related competences			
H1: Knowledge of legal framework	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understands the most important EU directives relevant to ELSI (e.g. ethics checklist for H2020; animal welfare directive; copyright; data protection; health and safety for visitors - especially for those requiring physical access to infrastructure; industry codes; declaration of Helsinki) • Understands relevant standard operating procedures • Understands principles of client liability and the 	ELI - don't know whether courses available on this	P, C, O

	<p>need to comply with local policy</p> <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can identify legal challenges and knows who to consult to check the relevant legislation • Can judge when it is advisable to consult a legal expert • Contributes to organisational risk management <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complies with legal frameworks and supports others to do so • Demonstrates honesty and integrity • Is open to continuous learning • Educates/informs fellow staff members and/or users of infrastructure to ensure that they understand the need for legal compliance and the consequences of breaching this <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is not aware of relevant legal frameworks and does not show respect for the need to comply with them • Does not encourage others to respect legal frameworks 		
<p>H2: Understanding of the organisational ethical framework</p>	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appreciation of the basic ethical principles underlying research in the RI's field • Working knowledge of the code of conduct of own organisation <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifies and implements relevant ethical behaviours associated with the organisation's ethical framework; knows who in the organisation to raise sensitive issues with • Good documentation practice <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is aware of, implements and reflects on ethical guidelines in day-to-day work • Demonstrates awareness of sensitive data • Proactively accepts patient requests in line with public engagement <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates lack of interest in, and 	<p>ELI: course needs to be developed</p>	<p>C, O</p>

	<p>understanding of, the ethical framework of the organisation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not 'live' the code of conduct • Demonstrates no understanding about what is sensitive data (what sensitive data means depends on the context!) • Is insensitive to requests on transparency or disclosure of procedures from stakeholders (e.g. patients) 		
H3: Communication with agencies and ethical boards	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understands the regulatory framework for the ethical conduct of research (likely to be national) • Understands that there may be national and organisational differences in ethical frameworks, and knows who to consult to ensure that these are upheld • Is aware of relevant regulatory frameworks <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applies relevant regulatory frameworks to own projects <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consults appropriately with agencies and ethical boards <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not make use of ethical expertise, and does not encourage others to do so • Shows lack of respect for ethical guidelines 	ELI: no courses	P, C, O
H4: Handling of confidential information	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understands what confidential information is and why it is important to respect confidentiality • Appreciates the difference between confidential and sensitive information • Is aware of confidentiality rules within the organisation and broader business context <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applies organisational and broader confidentiality guidelines effectively and can reinterpret them in the same spirit for new projects • Complies with IT and other security guidelines <p>Effective behaviours</p>	ELI: Courses on IT? Yes; Social?	P, C, O

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates honesty and integrity • Complies with both the spirit and the letter of confidentiality guidelines • Respects confidentiality - knows when and how to use confidential information without abusing the confidence of the source <p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not respect the confidentiality of information gained through the normal duties 		
<p>H5: Understanding the innovation cycle (aligned with Rltrain)</p>	<p>Knowledge base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broad awareness of the innovation cycle and how it applies within the organisation or broader business context • Awareness of relevant regulatory frameworks and who to consult within the organisation regarding intellectual property rights • Appreciates the dynamics of knowledge-intensive environments and the need to protect the organisation's IPR • Designs service models for innovation and keeps up to date with technical developments in the field • Appreciates the need for Data management and protection in the context of innovation <p>Skills base</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open mindset • Applies technical knowledge to translate an agreed vision for a new product into a viable product • Identifies and communicates problems early; recognises when they have the potential to derail an innovative project • Engages with others to realise the vision for a new product, taking on board the need for change as the project progresses <p>Effective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates adaptability throughout the innovation cycle • Is open to IP issues • Keeps appropriate records • Recognizes the potential commercial value of research and applies organisational values to innovation 	<p>ELI: courses available</p>	<p>P, C, O</p>

	<p>Ineffective behaviours</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not recognise potential commercial value of research and does not protect IPR in accordance with organisational guidelines/values • Is too internally focused, doesn't recognise the environment signals and innovation trends 		
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Next steps

Our next steps are to perform a gap analysis by mapping our competency profile against existing training in the on-course® database (D9.2) and then to develop training to fill the gaps. We will continue to align our data science training needs with those of EDISON. We participated in a workshop at the Core Technologies for the Life Sciences Conference in Heidelberg on 15 June. This identified several synergies, and the newly formed CTLS society now has a training working group which plans to align its activities with those of CORBEL WP9.

Publications

No publications as a result of this deliverable.

Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed:

The delay is mainly due to the fact that Rltrain and CORBEL WP9 are so much interlinked. This has generated some delays in finishing the competency profiles for CORBEL and the mapping of existing courses. There were also some staffing issues within EBI which soon will be solved, but did not allow to finalize that work within the originally proposed time frame.

Adjustments made

N/A

Appendices

Appendix 1: Training needs survey distributed to ESFRI and EIROForum RIs. The questions of particular relevance to CORBEL WP9 are highlighted in yellow.

Training needs for management and leadership of Research Infrastructures

Welcome Page

This survey has been developed by **RItrain**, a new EU-funded project to develop management and leadership training for research infrastructures in Europe. The European Commission has recognised that professional development of managers, engineers and technicians working in research infrastructures needs to be stimulated, and we need your input to ensure that the training developed by RItrain addresses the highest training priorities for your research infrastructure.

We are gathering input from infrastructures supporting research in many different areas, and at different levels of maturity, from initial planning to operational maturity. We recognise that training needs change with time, and that they are different for distributed versus single-site infrastructures. For distributed infrastructures, training needs may vary depending on the size or the nature of each site.

The results of this survey will be used to shape a training programme that is tailored to these needs. Participants in the survey will gain early access to this training and will play a vital role in helping us to optimise it. We value your contribution and look forward to sharing the outcomes with you.

The survey should take no more than 10-15 minutes of your time to complete; questions with an asterisk require a response and it would be immensely helpful if you could spare the time to respond fully to all questions.

Training needs for management and leadership of Research Infrastructures

Part 1: About you

*** 1. Which research infrastructure do you represent?**

*** 2. What is your role within your research infrastructure?**

- Director/coordinator
- Project manager
- Managerial/administrative staff
- Technical staff**
- Training coordinator
- Other (please specify)

3. Can we contact you?

Email Address

If you would like to be contacted in the future with a report on the results of this survey, and on future training opportunities for RI management and leadership, please provide your email address. We will not distribute this to other parties.

Training needs for management and leadership of Research Infrastructures

Part 2: About your research infrastructure

*** 4. What type of research does your infrastructure support?**

- Biomedical sciences/health and food
- E-infrastructure
- Energy
- Environmental sciences
- Materials and analytical sciences
- Physical sciences and engineering
- Social sciences and humanities
- Other (please specify)

Check all that apply.

*** 5. What stage in its life cycle do you consider your research infrastructure to have reached?**

- Planning phase
- Construction phase
- Operational phase - early (within 5 years of construction)
- Operational maturity
- Other (please specify)

6. How broad is your user community?

- Regional (within one country)
- National
- Pan-European
- Global
- Other (please specify)

7. How many employees does your RI (for single-site infrastructures) or your division/node of the RI (for distributed infrastructures) have now?

- 1-20
- 21-100
- 101-1000
- 1001+

8. How many employees do you anticipate that your RI (for single-site infrastructures) or your division/node of the RI (for distributed infrastructures) will have by the end of 2020?

- 1-20
- 21-100
- 101-1000
- 1001+

Training needs for management and leadership of Research Infrastructures

Staff in management and leadership

Please provide an estimate for people in each of the specified roles. Numbers refer to full-time equivalents.

9. How many staff do you currently have in management and leadership?

	1	2-5	6-10	11-20	21-50	51+
Director/CEO	<input type="radio"/>					
Finance	<input type="radio"/>					
Technical operations (including IT)	<input type="radio"/>					
Non-technical operations (inc. Administration and HR)	<input type="radio"/>					
Communications and training	<input type="radio"/>					
Other (please specify)	<input type="radio"/>					

Other (please specify)

Please provide an estimate for people in each of the specified roles. Numbers refer to full-time equivalents.

10. How many staff do you anticipate having in management and leadership by the end of 2020?

	1	2-5	6-10	11-20	21-50	51+
Director/CEO	<input type="radio"/>					
Finance	<input type="radio"/>					
Technical operations (including IT)	<input type="radio"/>					
Non-technical operations (inc. Administration and HR)	<input type="radio"/>					
Communications and training	<input type="radio"/>					
Other (please specify)	<input type="radio"/>					

Other (please specify)

11. How many physical sites does your infrastructure have?

- 1
- 2-5
- 6-10
- 11-20
- 21+

Training needs for management and leadership of Research Infrastructures

Competency in which of the following areas is important to your managerial and leadership staff?

* 12. Leading the organisation

- Setting and adhering to organisational values
- Strategic and operational planning
- Project management (especially in a transnational context)
- Ethical and legal compliance; equality, social and cultural awareness
- Income and funding generation
- Financial management and budgetary control
- Understanding the legal landscape (international contractual law, IP law, etc.)
- Staff recruitment, management and development
- Infrastructure and resource management (including data management and security)
- Innovation and business development (including developing new services and technologies)
- Service provision (including service level agreements, quality control, physical access to services, user training)
- Impact assessment
- Public procurement
- Stakeholder management (including user communities, policymakers, Board of Governors etc.)
- Other (please specify)

*** 13. Engagement (within and beyond the organization)**

- Communication, outreach and advocacy
- Negotiation skills
- Collaboration and networking (including in a global context, and between sectors)
- Conflict management
- Leading change
- Leading diverse and multidisciplinary teams (Motivation, delegation, etc.)
- Other (please specify)

*** 14. Professional conduct**

- Integrity and responsibility
- Ability to take difficult decisions
- Responsiveness
- Career management and commitment to professional development
- Effective delegation of tasks
- Time management
- Other (please specify)

Training needs for management and leadership of Research Infrastructures

The highest priority training need

*** 15. For each role, please select the highest priority training need and summarise what your infrastructure would be able to do (or be able to do better) as a consequence of the training**

Highest training priority

Director/CEO		▼
Finance		▼
Technical operations (including IT)		▼
Non-technical operations (inc. Administration and HR)		▼
Communications and training		▼
Other (please specify)		▼

Other (please specify)

16. Please summarise what your infrastructure would be able to do (or be able to do better) as a consequence of the training (at least 50 words). Role: Director/CEO

17. Please summarise what your infrastructure would be able to do (or be able to do better) as a consequence of the training (at least 50 words). Role: Finance

18. Please summarise what your infrastructure would be able to do (or be able to do better) as a consequence of the training (at least 50 words). Role: Technical operations (including IT)

19. Please summarise what your infrastructure would be able to do (or be able to do better) as a consequence of the training (at least 50 words). Role: Non-technical operations (inc. Administration and HR)

20. Please summarise what your infrastructure would be able to do (or be able to do better) as a consequence of the training (at least 50 words). Role: Communications and training

21. Please summarise what your infrastructure would be able to do (or be able to do better) as a consequence of the training (at least 50 words). Role: Other (please specify)

Training needs for management and leadership of Research Infrastructures

Training formats

22. What training formats do you feel would most benefit you and your peers?

- Short, intensive sessions off site (<2 consecutive days)
- Short, intensive sessions at your own site (<2 consecutive days)
- Pre- and/or post-course tasks or projects
- Interactive online events (e.g. webinars)
- Online tutorials and pre-recorded videos
- Short visits to sites with expertise in a specific area (<2 consecutive days)
- Project-based work at a site with expertise in a specific area (1 week +)
- Networking sessions with peers from other RIs
- Other (please specify)

23. If you could choose only one, what would be your preferred format?

* 24. How much time in total (including any work before or after training events) would a typical member of your management and leadership team be prepared to put into training over the period of a year?

No time	up to a week of continuous work	up to a week of discontinuous work	up to a month of continuous work	up to a month of discontinuous work	up to three months of continuous work	up to three months of discontinuous work	more than three months of continuous work	more than three months of discontinuous work
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

25. How much would your organisation be prepared to pay for training?

- Would not be prepared to pay
- Up to €50 per day of contact time (excluding travel and accommodation)
- Up to €100 per day of contact time (excluding travel and accommodation)
- Other (please specify)

26. What other factors influence your choice of training?

- Certification
- Location
- Reputation of the organisation delivering the training
- Testimonials from people whose opinion I respect
- Selection for people at my level or higher
- No selection - I'm the best judge of whether I'll benefit
- Opportunities to exchange knowledge with people like me
- Opportunities to learn from a recognised leader in the field
- Other (please specify)

Check any that apply.

*** 27. Who are you responding to this survey on behalf of?**

- A. An entire single-site infrastructure
- B. An entire distributed/multi-site infrastructure
- C. The coordinating site/hub of a distributed/multi-site infrastructure
- D. One node/non-coordinating site of a distributed/multi-site infrastructure (please specify name of node)
- Other (please specify)
D. Please specify name of node

Training needs for management and leadership of Research Infrastructures

Part 3: About current training for your management and leadership staff

Part 3: Please give your answers only if you answered A or B in Question 3:

Q3: Who are you responding to this survey on behalf of?

A. An entire single-site infrastructure

B. An entire distributed/multi-site infrastructure

*** 28. Does your research infrastructure currently provide managerial and leadership training for its staff?**

- A. Yes - provided in-house
- B. Yes - provided by the organisation that hosts our research infrastructure
- C. Yes - provided by external commercial suppliers
- D. No formal programme but staff have identified courses and the infrastructure has funded people to attend them
- E. No training programme now but we are planning to offer one
- F. No training programme now and no plans to offer one
- G. Don't know

Please use this box to provide any additional information on managerial and leadership training that your RI has found valuable.

29. Would your RI be willing to offer some places to staff from other RIs as part of a collaboration in which your staff also had access to training provided by other RIs?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Comments

Training needs for management and leadership of Research Infrastructures

If your RI offers its own training, which areas do you consider it to excel in?

30. Leading the organisation

- Setting and adhering to organisational values
- Strategic and operational planning
- Project management (especially in a transnational context)
- Ethical and legal compliance; equality, social and cultural awareness
- Income and funding generation
- Financial management and budgetary control
- Understanding the legal landscape (international contractual law, IP law, etc.)
- Staff recruitment, management and development
- Infrastructure and resource management (including data management and security)
- Innovation and business development (including developing new services and technologies)
- Service provision (including service level agreements, quality control, physical access to services, user training)
- Impact assessment
- Public procurement
- Stakeholder management (including user communities, policymakers, Board of Governors etc.)
- Other (please specify)

31. Engagement (within and beyond the organization)

- Communication, outreach and advocacy
- Negotiation skills
- Collaboration and networking (including in a global context, and between sectors)
- Conflict management
- Leading change
- Leading diverse and multidisciplinary teams (Motivation, delegation, etc.
- Other (please specify)

32. Professional conduct

- Integrity and responsibility
- Ability to take difficult decisions
- Responsiveness
- Career management and commitment to professional development
- Effective delegation of tasks
- Time management
- Other (please specify)

Training needs for management and leadership of Research Infrastructures

Contribution and hosting

33. Would your organisation be prepared to contribute trainers to RItrain in areas where your research infrastructure has recognised expertise?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Comments

34. Would your organisation be prepared to host short-term visits from small delegations of managerial staff from other organisations?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Comments

35. Do you have any other thoughts or comments?

36. Contact

First Name

Last Name

Role

Email Address

Training needs for management and leadership of Research Infrastructures

Add another contact

You can add here up to three additional contacts.

37. Contact #1

First Name

Last Name

Role

Email Address

38. Contact #2

First Name

Last Name

Role

Email Address

39. Contact #3

First Name

Last Name

Role

Email Address

Training needs for management and leadership of Research Infrastructures

Thank you message!

Thank you for completing this survey! The results will be used to shape a training programme that is tailored to the training needs of managers and leaders of research infrastructure. Participants in the survey who have shared their contact details with us will gain early access to this training and will play a vital role in helping us to optimise it. We value your contribution and look forward to sharing the outcomes with you.